

FORMULATION DEVELOPMENT AND EVALUATION OF ILAPRAZOLE MULTIPLE EMULSION

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ABSTARCT

Emulsions are heterogeneous systems composed of two immiscible or inadequately miscible liquid phases, where one liquid is dispersed in the form of droplets within the other. These systems can be broadly classified into simple emulsions such as oil-in-water (O/W) or water-in-oil (W/O) emulsions, as well as more complex or multiple emulsions including water-in-oil-in-water (W/O/W) and oil-in-water-in-oil (O/W/O) types. Additionally, specialized forms like microemulsions and fine emulsions exist, which differ mainly in droplet size and stability characteristics. Among these, W/O/W multiple emulsions have attracted considerable interest in pharmaceutical research as effective drug delivery systems. In this study, the drug Ilaprazole, a proton pump inhibitor is used to reduce gastric acid secretion, was utilized to formulate multiple emulsions. Different surfactant combinations were tested to optimize the emulsion characteristics. The first set included formulations F1, F2, and F3, which were prepared using varying ratios of Span and Tween surfactants: F1 (Span 40: Tween 80), F2 (Span 60: Tween 80), and F3 (Span 80: Tween 80), all in a 3:5 ratio. Another set of emulsions—F4, F5, F6, and F7—were prepared with different Span and Tween combinations: F4 (Span 40: Tween 40), F5 (Span 40: Tween 20), F6 (Span 40: Tween 40), and F7 (Span 40: Tween 60), in a 5:7 ratio. Among them, formulation F7 exhibited the most desirable characteristics, providing a slow and steady release of Ilaprazole compared to the other formulations. Due to its superior performance, F7 was selected and further optimized as the preferred formulation for sustained drug delivery.

KEYWORDS: Multiple Emulsions, Ilaprazole, Emulsifying agent, formulation approach, evaluation, surfactant.

1. INTRODUCTION^[1]

Emulsions may be described as heterogeneous systems, one immiscible liquid is dispersed in the form of droplets and stabilized by a third constituent called emulsifying agent. These two liquids are also chemically nonreactive and form the systems that are characterized by a low thermodynamically stability.

Based on their formation, emulsions can be divided into:

1. Simple Emulsions.
2. Multiple Emulsions.

1. SIMPLE EMULSION

Simple Emulsions can be separated according to their continuous phase or dispersed phases

Simple emulsion types

A] Oil-in-water emulsions (O/W) - where oil is the disperse phase in a continuous phase of water.

B] Water-in-oil emulsions (W/O) - where water is the disperse phase in a continuous phase of oil.

2. MULTIEMULSION

Multiple emulsions are novel carrier systems which are complex, polydisperse, multiphase systems consisting of at least two immiscible liquids i.e., both w/o and o/w emulsions exists simultaneously in a single system.

Lipophilic and hydrophilic surfactants are used for stabilizing these two emulsions respectively. The droplets of dispersed phase contain even smaller dispersed droplets themselves, thus also called as "emulsions of emulsions". The inner dispersed droplets in multiple emulsions are separated from outer liquid phase by a layer of another phase. The solute has to transverse from inner miscible phase to outer miscible phase via middle immiscible organic phase, prior to release at absorption site, thus also known as liquid membrane system. Partition and diffusion coefficient of drug and strength of middle membrane phase, which is a multimolecular layer of oil, water and emulsifier at both the interfaces of multiple emulsion, controls the drug release from these systems. This extends the classical definition to include "liquid droplets and/or liquid crystals dispersed in liquid".

These are heterogeneous preparation composed of two immiscible liquids, i.e. oil and water, one of which is dispersed as fine droplets uniformly throughout the other. The phase presented as small droplets are called dispersed, discontinuous or internal phase and the supporting liquid is known as continuous or external phase. Droplet diameter in multiple emulsions may range from 0.1 to 100 μm . It consists of large and poly dispersed droplets that are thermodynamically unstable with a strong tendency for coalescence, flocculation and creaming. This may lead emulsions to reverse back to separate oil and water phase by fusion or coalescence of droplets, thus it is required to add third component which kinetically stabilizes multiple emulsions, known as emulsifying agent/emulsifier.^[2]

Multiple emulsions are prepared from oil and water by emulsification of an existing emulsion so as to provide two dispersed phases. These emulsions have promising applications in various fields such as chemistry, pharmaceuticals, cosmetics etc., and have also been investigated as controlled-release drug delivery systems (ODDS), as, "emulsion liquid membranes" for various

applications. These may be used as intermediate products in preparation of inorganic particles, lipid nanoparticles, polymeric microspheres, biodegradable microspheres, gel microbeads and vesicles such as polymerosomes. Many potential pharmaceutical applications for multiple emulsions are aimed for slow and sustained release of active matter from an internal reservoir into continuous phase. They can also serve as an internal reservoir to entrap matter from outer diluted continuous phase into inner confined space. The active matter will dissolve in part in inner phase, in part at the internal and occasionally at external interface. Protection of sensitive and active molecules from oxidation in external phase can also be observed.^[3,4]

Types

Based on nature of dispersed medium multiple emulsions are of two types, oil-in-water-in-oil (O/W/O) and water in-oil-in-water (W/O/W) microemulsion and fine emulsion. The most common multiple emulsions are W/O/W type, however for some specific applications O/W/O emulsions can also be used.

W/O/W emulsion system

In W/O/W system, an organic phase (hydrophobic) separates internal and external aqueous phases. In other words, W/O/W is a system in which oil droplets may be surrounded by an aqueous phase, which in turn encloses one or more water droplets. The immiscible oil phase, which separates two miscible aqueous phases is known as "liquid membrane" and acts as a diffusion barrier and semi permeable membrane for the drugs or moieties entrapped in internal aqueous phase.

O/W/O emulsion system^[5]

In O/W/O system, an aqueous phase (hydrophilic) separates internal and external oil phase. In other words, O/W/O is a system in which water droplets may be surrounded in oil phase, which in turn encloses one or more oil droplets.

Figure 1: Types of multiple emulsion.

ADVANTAGES^[6]

1. They mask the bitter taste and odour of drugs, thereby making them more palatable. E.g. Castor oil, Cod-liver oil, Chloroquine and Phosphate etc.
2. Prolongs release of drug, thereby providing sustained release action.
3. Essential nutrients like carbohydrates, fats and vitamins can all be emulsified.

- Can be administered to bed ridden patients as sterile intravenous emulsions.
- Provides protection to drugs which are susceptible to oxidation or hydrolysis.
- Enhancement of enteric or dermal absorption.
- Hydrophilic as well as hydrophobic drugs can be entrapped.
- Enhances bioavailability and thus increase in drug dosing intervals.
- Emulsions are used widely to formulate externally used products like lotions, creams, liniments.

DISADVANTAGES^[6]

- These are packaged in a plastic/glass container, so care should be taken in handling and storage
- Liable to microbial contamination which can lead to cracking.
- Uniform and accurate dose may not be achieved.

LIMITATIONS OF MULTIEMULSION^[7]

The main problem associated with multiple emulsions is their thermodynamic instability and their complex structure, which has severely limited their usefulness in the many applications of multiple emulsions.

2. DRUG PROFILE^[18-21]

Ilaprazole

- † Therapeutic category : Proton pump inhibitor
- † Empirical formula : $C_{19}H_{18}N_4O_2S$
- † Molecular weight : 366.436820 g/mol CAS NO : 172152-36-2

❖ Structural formula

3. EXCIPIENT USED – Span 40, Span 60, Span 80, Tween 20, Tween 40, Tween 80, Liquid Paraffin, Methyl Paraben.

4. MATERIAL AND EQUIPMENT USED

Materials used

The following drug, excipients and chemical were used. Ilaprazole, Span 40, Span 60, Span 80, Tween 20, Tween 40, Tween 60, Tween 80, Liquid paraffine, Methyl parabane, Distilled water, HCL.

Equipment used

The following equipments were used.

Table no. 1: Name of equipment used for formulation of oral multiple emulsion of Ilaprazole.

Sr No	Name of equipment	Manufacturer/Supplier
1	Homogenizer	IKA T25
2	Weighing balance	PHOENIX
3	Magnetic stirrer	REMI
4	UV Spectrophotometer	SHIMADZU CORP
5	Franz Diffusion cell	Labs India, Mumbai
6	Beaker	-
7	Measuring Cylinder	-
8	Volumetric flask	-

5. EXPERIMENTAL WORK^[24]

5.1. Preformulation Study of Ilaprazole

Preformulation studies is an investigation of physical & chemical properties of drug substance alone and when combined with excipient Preformulation involves the application of biopharmaceutical principles to the physicochemical parameters of drug substance are characterized with the goal of designing optimum drug delivery system.

The objective of present work is to development and evaluation of multiple emulsion of ilaprazole for oral drug delivery. The drug Preformulation studies were carried out like organoleptic characteristic, melting point, solubility, UV spectrophotometer and callibration to find out that the various functional groups are same as the standard drug. UV maxima of drug were found out by using Shimadzu Corp UV. -Physical characterization of drug sample:

5.2. Organoleptic characteristics of drug

The drug (Ilaprazole) powder was examined for its organoleptic properties like colour, odour, melting point, PH.

5.3. Solubility Data Of Drug

The solubility of the drug sample was carried out in different sample according to Indian pharmacopeia 2015. The result was then compared with those given in the official book.

5.4. Organoleptic characteristics of multiple emulsion

The organoleptic characteristics of multiple emulsion was carried out for colour, odour, taste and Ph.

5.5. UV Analysis

Determination of λ_{max}

Ilaprazole was dissolved in 0.1 N HCL buffer solution and dissolution were made. It was scanned on UV visible spectrometer in the range of 200-400 nm to obtain λ_{max} of Ilaprazole.

5.6 Determination of Calibration Curve

1) Preparation of standard stock solution

A standard stock solution containing 1000 μ g/ml was prepared by dissolving 100 mg of Ilaprazole in 100 ml of 0.1N. HCl solution.

2) **Preparation of the test solution:** The standard stock solution containing 1000 μ g/ml of Ilaprazole, was prepared in 0.1 N HCl, from this, stock solution was pipette out and dilutions were prepared as 10, 20, 30, 40, 50 μ g/ml and absorbance was taken at 305 nm.

5.7 METHOD OF PREPARATION

Multiple emulsions were prepared by two step emulsification process

A. Preparation of Primary Emulsification. B. Secondary Emulsification

A. Primary Emulsification

10 ml of distilled water containing 0.03 g of drug was gradually added to 14 ml of oil phase containing primary emulsifier (span 40) and 0.03 g of drug with continuous stirring at 5000 rpm for 5 minutes. It gives the primary emulsion.

B. Secondary Emulsification

20ml of viscous primary emulsion was emulsified further with an external aqueous phase containing secondary emulsifier (tween 40) and 0.03 g drug with continuous stirring at 3000rpm for 8 minutes. All the formulations were prepared by following the same procedure.

Effect of primary emulsifier was observed by evaluating several formulations.

Table no. 2: Formulation of oral multiple emulsion of Ilaprazole.

Ingredient							
	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7
Ilaprazole	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06
Span 40	0.6	-	-	1	1	1	1
Span 60	-	0.6	-	-	-	-	-
Span 80	-	-	0.6	-	-	-	-
Tween 20	-	-	-	-	1.4	-	-
Tween 40	-	-	-	-	-	1.4	-
Tween 60	-	-	-	-	-	-	1.4
Tween 80	1	1	1	1.4	-	-	-
Liquid paraffin	14	14	14	14	14	14	14
Methyl paraben	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05
Distilled water	30	30	30	30	30	30	30

(1 Dose= 5ml)

5.8. In vitro drug release study^[25]

The in vitro drug release study was carried out on a simple dissolution cell using cellophane membrane (thickness-200 μ m, breaking strength-2.7 kgf/cm). Prior to release studies, the cellophane membrane was soaked in distilled water for 6 hours washed frequently 4 times by changing distilled water, then immersed in 56 v buffers lotion for at least 60 min and washed finally with 5 portions of distilled water. 15 ml freshly prepared multiple emulsion was added to donor chamber, made up of a hollow glass tube (2.5 cm in diameter and 10 cm in length) and membrane was tied on becoml end of the tube with a nylon string. This tube was dipped into 250 ml vessel containing 100 ml of PBS pH 1.2 and magnetic stirrer and maintained at 37 °C which acted as receiving chamber. Aliquots of 1ml were collected from receiving chamber at predetermined time intervals and the drug content was determined on UV spectrophotometer at 305 nm after suitable dilution.

Fig. 2: Franz diffusion cell.

This diffusion cell is the most common of all Franz Cells. It is a jacketed Franz Cell with a 9 mm orifice diameter, flat ground joint, and 5ml receptor volume. It is the de facto standard for working with human skin and may be used with any membrane 4mm or less in thickness.

In vitro dissolution studies for (F1-F7) batch were carried out using Franz diffusion cell Method, in 14 ml of phosphate buffer of pH 7.4 as dissolution media and

release profile data was analysed for cumulative percent dissolved at different time intervals given in Table No 3

6. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

6.1 The organoleptic characteristics of drug

- The colour of the drug was found to be pale yellow as mention in the Indian pharmacopeia 2015.
- The odour of the drug was bitter as mention in the Indian pharmacopeia 2015.
- The taste of the drug was tasteless as mention in the Indian pharmacopeia 2015.
- Melting point of drug was 183-1860 C as mention in the Indian pharmacopeia 2015
- The PH of drug was 10.2 as mention in the Indian pharmacopeia 2015.

6.2 Solubility: The drug was freely soluble in dichloromethane, soluble in methanol and slightly soluble in water.

6.3 Organoleptic characteristics of multiple emulsion

- The colour of multiple emulsion was found to be off white.
- The odour of multiple emulsion was found to be bitter.
- The taste of the multiple emulsion was found to be tasteless.
- The PH of emulsion of found to be 10.4.

6.4 Spectroscopy

As Ilaprazole was scanned in UV visible Spectroscopy 200-400 and maximum absorbance was found at 305 nm. It match with standard of result from IP 2015.

Fig. no. 3: Calibration curve of Ilaprazole.

Fig. 4: Standard calibration curve of ilaprazole.

6.5 DRUG RELEASE

Table no. 3: Cumulative % Drug release.

TIME IN MIUNTES	FORMULATION						
	% drug release						
Time (min)	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
15	0.02	0.03	0.03	0.04	0.02	0.03	0.02
30	0.39	0.3	0.3	0.25	0.44	0.38	0.41
45	0.67	0.77	0.67	0.86	0.96	0.77	0.81
60	1.15	1.05	1.15	1.34	1.24	1.24	1.19
75	21.31	9.58	23.43	18.41	13.1	17.495	10.75
90	33.04	33.92	27.45	22.98	14.41	24.037	11.94
105	41.85	45.84	32.3	26.9	31.29	34.698	13.74

120	53.09	57.82	37.24	21.29	47.61	39.432	21.76
135	61.62	61.63	41.56	25.58	64.15	45.208	23.74
150	68.13	73.24	46.71	38.89	75.31	53.54	25.48
175	71.9	78.42	52.42	42.98	85.45	72.474	33.41
190	80.11	80.02	58.63	45.27	89.8	79.129	41.71
205	95.03	91.62	64.56	59.18	95.33	85.964	47.16
220			72.45	62.92		95.232	51.92
235			79.43	77.07		100.3	68.85
250			84.49	80.69			78.39

Fig. 5: Drug release of batch F1 to F4.

Fig. 6: Drug release of batch F5 to F7.

6.6 OPTIMIZATION

In the present study various surfactant & preservatives used in the combination and in different ratio. In the study of this formulation F1 to F6 is given slow and gradual release over time. Batch F7 exhibited negligible absorbance up to 1.30 hours, followed by a slow and steady increase in absorbance over the next 4 hours, indicating its stability and controlled drug release profile.

7. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

Multiple emulsions have been proposed to have numerous uses including their use for enhancement of bioavailability or as a prolonged drug delivery system. But the inherent instability of this system needs to be overcome before they find potential application in

pharmaceuticals. Multiple emulsions are often stabilized using a combination of preservatives surfactants. The ratio of these surfactants is important in achieving stable multiple emulsions. Ilaprazole has low bioavailability; few studies have been reported for enhancement of Bioavailability of poorly water soluble drugs by formulating as multiple emulsions. The present study is based on the hypothesis that improvement of in vitro dissolution profile will reflect the enhancement of bioavailability of the drug.

The investigations presented lead us to conclude that the multiple emulsions prepared using Ilaprazole and surfactants like Span 20, span40, span60, span80, Tween 20, Tween 40, Tween 60, and Tween 80 by two step

emulsification methods. To find out the mechanism of drug release from multiple emulsions. The Ilaprazole which thereby reduce dose frequency, decrease side effect and improved patient compliance.

8. Future scope

Batch F7 demonstrated slow, steady, and extended drug release, with approximately 70% release over 4 hours, suggesting its potential for further investigation in sustained and controlled release formulations.

The formulation can subsequently be evaluated in animal models for confirmatory studies.

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